

Effect of Supplementation Different Levels of Fermented Barley by Kiwi Juice in Broiler Diets on Growth Performance, Physiological Traits, Gut Microbiota and Liver Enzymes Activity

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Abstract. The study was conducted in the poultry farm of the Department of Animal Production/College of Agricultural Engineering Sciences/ University of Baghdad. The current research aimed to study the role of fermenting barley seeds with kiwi juice to improve the nutritional value of barley and the potential to replace it with corn on the growth performance, gut microbiota and some physiological blood characteristics and liver enzyme activity of broiler chickens. A total of 200 broiler chicks (Ross 308) one day old were used in the study. The chicks were divided into four treatment groups, each group contained 50 chicks with five replicates for each treatment (10 chicks per replicate, and each replicate containing 6 males and 4 females). The treatment groups were as follows: The G1 (control group) received a basal diet. G2, G3 and G4 treatments were basal diet + replacing 10, 20 and 30% fermented barley with yellow corn respectively. The results showed no significant differences between all treatment groups (G2, G3 and G4) that fed partially fermented barley compared with the G1 group (free treatment) in final body weight, total weight gain, total diet consumption and diet conversion ratio. No significant differences were observed in the total numbers of beneficial and harmful microorganisms and physiological characteristics in all study treatments, while a significant improvement was observed for the treated birds (G4) in liver enzyme activity AST compared with control treatment G1. It can be concluded that fermented barley with kiwi juice improved the nutritional value of barley and the performance of broilers and partially replaced with yellow corn in broiler diets would be great to increase the number of feedstuffs.

Keywords. Broiler, Fermented barley, Kiwi juice, Growth performance, Gut microbiota, Physiological parameters, Liver enzyme activity.

1. Introduction

The poultry industry has rapidly witnessed, a significant development in the methods and techniques used to improve production and its quality, as these methods and techniques used today are different from those used ten years ago, and every new day that passes witnesses a quantitative and qualitative development in various farms of the poultry industry. Therefore, it received the poultry industry interest in many countries of the world due to the continuous increase in population and the increased demand for animal protein at low prices [1]. Poultry nutrition is one of the pillars of this industry, which has witnessed extensive and influential developments in improving production by setting precise standards for manufacturing diet and controlling it to meet the most precise daily needs of birds [2].

The high cost of imported diet ingredients and their scarcity of availability are one of the problems facing the poultry industry, so it's become necessary to think about local alternatives, improve existing ones, raise their nutritional value and make them more beneficial when consumed by poultry. Therefore, using alternatives to imported and expensive materials such as yellow corn will reduce the costs of diet. Among these alternatives is barley, which is available in large quantities can be used in poultry diet and not suitable for human use [3].

Barley is a preferred cereal crop in many parts of the world because of its drought resistance and ability to mature in climates with a short growing season. Barley varieties without a crop plan are successfully grown on a commercial scale in some countries [4]. So, barley is one of the common material used in animal diet, unless this diet material is not free of food inhibitors, which are among the most important problems facing nutritionists due to their negative effects on poultry. It also limits or reduces the use of raw diet materials, and these inhibitors include non-starch polysaccharides, mannan compounds, beta-glucan, xylan, tannic acid, and phytic acid. The presence of these inhibitors affects the degree of digestion and absorption of the diet material and also increases the viscosity of the digestive tract [5-6]. Barley grains contain a high percentage of non-starchy polysaccharides that are soluble in water, especially the beta-glucan compound (B_Glucan) and it also contains a percentage of fiber 16.66% [6,7].

To increase the percentage of barley in poultry diet, an improvement process must be carried such as fermentation [8]. Adding enzymes such as beta-mannan enzyme [9], The fermentation process contributes to increase protein and ether extract and reduce fiber, also reducing the level of nutritional inhibitors such as (phytic acid and tannin). In some grains, in addition to benefiting from some enzymes produced by microorganisms as a result of the fermentation process to improve the digestion coefficient. [6] reported that processing of fermenting barley grains with kiwi juice improves the nutritional value of barley and reduces the level of some inhibitors, as noted by [10] Some studies reported that using kiwi juice as a fermenting agent improves the nutritional value of potato peels.

Kiwi fruit contains many active compounds such as polyphenols and flavonoids. [11], and many vitamins and minerals [12], Also contains the enzyme actinidine which works to digest protein, as well as the enzyme bromelain, physin and stidine which play an important role in digesting fiber, Kiwi fruit also contains compounds with important oxidative action [13].

Despite the benefit of using kiwi fruit juice as a fermented agent, still, there are a paucity of information about fermented barley grain with kiwi juice. Therefore, this research aimed to study the effect of supplementation of different levels of fermented barley by kiwi juice in broiler diets on growth performance, physiological traits, gut microbiota and liver enzymes activity.

2. Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in the poultry farm of the Animal Production Department at the College of Agricultural Engineering Sciences, University of Baghdad operation with laboratories in The Ministry of Science and Technology Ethical approval No. ISO 17025 for 35 days, which the effect of fermenting barley grains with kiwi juice and introducing it into a broiler diet at rates of 10, 20, 30% was studied on growth performance, intestine microbial characteristics, some physiological characteristics and liver enzymes activity.

2.1. Fermentation Procedure

Barley grains were prepared from local markets and the fermentation process was carried out by following some steps, including washing the barley grains and then filtering them from water. After that, a 50 kg plastic container was used to put a quantity of barley in it and then water at a rate of 50% of the weight of the barley, before adding water to the barley, kiwi juice was prepared by using the kiwi fruit and removing the peels. Then the fruit was squeezed manually and then mixed with the amount of water to be added to the barley. The percentage of kiwi juice was 1% (1 kg kiwi sticks for every 100 kg barley), as it was PH Juice 2.66, then added to the barley and mixed well, followed by the process of filling the fermented barley in black polyethylene bags, and placed inside plastic containers, during the filling process, care was taken to press the barley grains to empty them from the air, and then close the bags tightly until ensuring as much as possible that the bag was free to air, after which the containers were left in a room with a temperature of 37 C for 10 days, after which the grains were emptied from the bags inside the plastic containers and spread on the concrete floor and left to dry in the shade with continuous stirring, picture (1). After completing the drying process, a sample was taken to the laboratory for chemical analysis as in Table (1).

Figure 1. Steps for fermenting and drying barley.

Table 1. Estimated chemical analysis of barley grains before and after fermentation.

Nutrient	Barley before fermentation	Barley after fermentation
Crude Protein %	12.11	12.5
C. EE Lipid %	2.15	2.31
Crude Fiber %	15.6	12.9
CHO%	57.2	56.8
Methiane mg/g	18.9	21.5
Lysine mg/g	80.4	85.9
Calcium %	28	32
Phosphor, avail %	240	258
Metabol.Energy k Cal	2705	2995
Tannic acid mg/g	22.5	18.9
Phytic acid mg/g	7.7	5.8

In the current experiment, a total of 200 broiler chicks (Ross 308) one day old were sexed and randomly distributed equally to the 4 treatment groups, each group contained 50 chicks with five replicates for each treatment (10 chicks per replicate, and each replicate containing 6 males and 4 females) with the average initial weight of the treatments being (G1, G2, G3, G4 It is 39.50, 38.95, 39.85, 39.53 g respectively). The chicks were raised according to the floor-rearing system, as the hall contains cages with dimensions of 100 x 120 cm width and length. The continuous lighting system (24 hours/day) was followed throughout the experiment, diet and water were provided freely. The chicks were fed on the starter diet from the age of 1 - 10 days, the growth diet from 11-24 days, and the finisher diet from 25 -35 days of bird life (Table 2,3,4).

The weight of the birds and the feed consumption at the end of each age period (start, growth and finisher) were recorded, and from there the weight gain rate and feed conversion ratio were calculated. At the age of 35 days, samples were taken from the birds, 5 birds in each treatment, and they were slaughtered. The intestinal contents were taken from them to calculate the numbers of beneficial and harmful bacteria and physiological characteristics. Blood samples were also drawn from the birds before slaughter from the wing vein, 5 birds from each treatment, after which some physiological characteristics were calculated. The data were statistically analyzed using the Statistical Analysis System-SAS (2018) was used to analyze data to study the effect of different treatments on the studied traits according to a completely randomized design (CRD), and the significant differences between the means were compared using [14].

Table 2. Composition calculated of starter diet 0-10 days for the experiment treatment groups.

Ingredients	G1	G2	G3	G4
yellow corn	57.2	47.6	38.1	28.5
Soybean meal 48% ¹	33.7	32.8	31.8	31
Plant protein concentrate 5% ²	5	5	5	5
barley	-	10	20	30
Vegetable oil	1.8	2,3	2.8	3,2
limestone	1,1	1,3	1,3	1,3
Dcp 21% ³	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.6
salt	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Vitamins and minerals ⁴	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Total	100	100	100	100
calculated chemical analysis				
Represented energy (kilocalories/kg)	3005.42	3006.77	3008,62	3003
Protein (%)	23.03	23.04	23	23.05
Lysine	1.33	1,288	1,14	1.20
Methionine	0.51	0.492	0.470	0.45
Calcium	0.95	0.97	0.96	0.96
Available phosphorus	0.52	0.50	0.41	0.43

(1) Protein concentrate type BROCON – 5 SPECIAL W. Each kg contains: 40% crude protein, 5% fat, 2.2% fiber, 4.2% calcium, 4.68% phosphorus, 3.85% lysine, 3.7% methionine, 4.12% methionine + cysteine, 2.5%

sodium, 2107 kcal/kg metabolized energy, 20000 IU vitamin A, 40000 IU vitamin D3, 500 mg vitamin E, 30 mg vitamin K3, 15 mg vitamin B1, 140 mg vitamin B2, 20 mg vitamin B6, 10 mg folic acid, 100 micrograms biotin, 1 mg iron, 100 mg copper, 1.2 mg manganese, 800 mg zinc, 15 mg Iodine, 2 mg Selenium, 6 mg Cobalt, 900 mg Antioxidant (BHG). (2) A mixture of vitamins and minerals, each kg contains: 500 IU Vitamin A, 600 IU D3, 10 mg E, 2 mg K3, 2 mg B1, 2 mg B2, 2 mg B6, 5 micrograms B12, 10 mg C, 15 mg Niacin, 500 micrograms Folic Acid. (3) According to the chemical analysis of the diet onaccording to [15].

Table 3. Composition calculated of grower diet 11-24 days for the experiment treatment groups.

Ingredients	G1	G2	G3	G4
yellow corn	60.3	50.7	41.1	31.7
Soybean meal 48% ¹	30	29.1	28.2	27.2
plant protein concentrate 5% ²	5	5	5	5
barley	-	10	20	30
Vegetable oil	2.7	3,2	3.7	4.1
limestone	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1
Dcp 21% ³	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
salt	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Vitamins and minerals ⁴	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Total	100	100	100	100
calculated chemical analysis				
Represented energy (kilocalories/kg)	3100	3101,34	3102.28	3100
Protein (%)	21.5	21.5	21.5	21.5
Lysine	1.23	1,188	1,13	1,10
Methionine	0.49	0.47	0.45	0.43
Calcium	0.87	0.87	0.86	0.86
Available phosphorus	0.438	0.43	0.42	0.41

(1) Protein concentrate type BROCON – 5 SPECIAL W. Each kg contains: 40% crude protein, 5% fat, 2.2% fiber, 4.2% calcium, 4.68% phosphorus, 3.85% lysine, 3.7% methionine, 4.12% methionine + cysteine, 2.5% sodium, 2107 kcal/kg metabolized energy, 20000 IU vitamin A, 40000 IU vitamin D3, 500 mg vitamin E, 30 mg vitamin K3, 15 mg vitamin B1, 140 mg vitamin B2, 20 mg vitamin B6, 10 mg folic acid, 100 micrograms biotin, 1 mg iron, 100 mg copper, 1.2 mg manganese, 800 mg zinc, 15 mg Iodine, 2 mg Selenium, 6 mg Cobalt, 900 mg Antioxidant (BHG). (2) A mixture of vitamins and minerals, each kg contains: 500 IU Vitamin A, 600 IU D3, 10 mg E, 2 mg K3, 2 mg B1, 2 mg B2, 2 mg B6, 5 micrograms B12, 10 mg C, 15 mg Niacin, 500 micrograms Folic Acid. (3) According to the chemical analysis of the diet onaccording to [15].

Table 4. Composition calculated of finisher diet 25-35 days for the experiment treatment groups.

Ingredients	G1	G2	G3	G4
yellow corn	64.5	55	45.4	35.9
Soybean meal 48% ¹	25.1	24.1	23.3	22.3
plant protein concentrate 5% ²	5	5	5	5
barley	-	10	20	30
Vegetable oil	3.6	4.1	4.5	5
limestone	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1
Dcp 21% ³	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
salt	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Vitamins and minerals ⁴	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Total	100	100	100	100
calculated chemical analysis				
Represented energy (kilocalories/kg)	3202.54	3204.39	3200	3200.62
Protein (%)	19.5	19.49	19.5	19.5
Lysine	1,103	1,1	1.00	1.00
Methionine	0.469	0.45	0.43	0.40
Calcium	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.80
Available phosphorus	0.39	0.39	0.38	0.37

(1) Protein concentrate type BROCON – 5 SPECIAL W. Each kg contains: 40% crude protein, 5% fat, 2.2% fiber, 4.2% calcium, 4.68% phosphorus, 3.85% lysine, 3.7% methionine, 4.12% methionine + cysteine, 2.5%

sodium, 2107 kcal/kg metabolized energy, 20000 IU vitamin A, 40000 IU vitamin D3, 500 mg vitamin E, 30 mg vitamin K3, 15 mg vitamin B1, 140 mg vitamin B2, 20 mg vitamin B6, 10 mg folic acid, 100 micrograms biotin, 1 mg iron, 100 mg copper, 1.2 mg manganese, 800 mg zinc, 15 mg Iodine, 2 mg Selenium, 6 mg Cobalt, 900 mg Antioxidant (BHG). (2) A mixture of vitamins and minerals, each kg contains: 500 IU Vitamin A, 600 IU D3, 10 mg E, 2 mg K3, 2 mg B1, 2 mg B2, 2 mg B6, 5 micrograms B12, 10 mg C, 15 mg Niacin, 500 micrograms Folic Acid. (3) According to the chemical analysis of the diet on according to [15].

2.2. Mathematical Model of the Experiment

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + T_i + e_{ij}$$

Since:

Y_{ij} : Viewing value j Return to transaction i .

μ : The overall average of the studied traits.

T_i : Effect of treatment i .

e_{ij} : A random error is normally distributed with a mean of zero and a variance of σ^2_e .

3. Results and Discussion

The current study found that feeding birds on fermented barley did not affect the body weight at age 10 and 35 days old compared to the control group (table 5). However, at age 24 days old, the G4 group which contains 30% fermented barley showed a significant increase in body weight compared to the G2, but there were no significant differences between the groups G4, G1 and G3 in the same period.

It is clear from Table (5) regarding the data on live body weight during the periods 10 and 35 days of the age of broiler chickens that there are no significant differences between all the treatments of using fermented barley and in the proportions (10, 20, 30%) compared to the control treatment G1 at the starter stage (10 days old), during the growth period at 24 days old, no significant differences were observed in live body weight between all treatments of replacing fermented barley with kiwi juice compared to the control treatment G1. While the second transaction was recorded G2 Containing 10% fermented barley, a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) in body weight compared to the fourth treatment G4 Which contains 30% fermented barley. As for the live body weight at the marketing age of 35 days, no significant differences were shown between all the treatments using fermented barley (G2, G3, G4) Compare with comparison treatment G1.

As for the rate of weight gain during the age stages, as well as the general rate, it is noted from Table (6) regarding the weight gain data, that there are no significant differences during the rearing stages (. -10), (11-24) and (25-35) days between all barley use treatments compared to the comparison group, but when calculating the cumulative rate from (. -35) days, there were also no significant differences between the various treatments.

As for the diet rates consumed by the birds in the treatments, it is noted from Table (7) that there is a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) In favor of the treatment of using fermented barley at a rate of 30% (G4) Compared with control treatment G1 While the fourth treatment did not differ (G4) With the second and third fermented barley treatments (G2, G3) And the transactions did not differ G 2, G 3 Morally significant in comparison treatment during the period from 0-10 days of birds' age.

During the period from 11 to 24 days of the birds' age, it is noted from the same table that there is a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) In the amount of diet consumed by treatment birds G3 containing 20% more fermented barley than the control treatment G1 While the treatment did not differ G3 Morally about G2, G4 The transactions also did not differ G2, G4 Morally about the transaction G1.

As for diet consumption during the period from 25-35 days and the total period from 0-35 days, it is noted that there are no significant differences between all treatments at different rates compared to the comparison treatment G1. With regard to the diet conversion factor, it is noted from the data in Table (8) that there are no significant differences between all four experimental coefficients during all rearing periods, as well as the cumulative period from 0-35 days.

It is noted from the results of the growth performance of broilers at the final period of 35 days of marketing age that there were no significant differences in live body weight, diet consumed and feed conversion ratio for all treatments of using fermented barley in broiler diets and for all ratios (10, 20,

30%) compared to the control treatment, as this result is positive and did not negatively affect the performance of the birds. This may be due to the fermentation process, which plays an important role in improving the nutritional value of barley, which caused an improvement in most of the nutritional elements, as in Table (1) of barley analysis. The fermentation process also reduced the level of some nutritional inhibitors, especially phytic acid and tannin, and reducing these inhibitors improves the nutritional value of barley, which is positively reflected in the performance of the birds, this is what was noted by [16]. The fermentation process with kiwi juice also plays an important role in improving the qualitative characteristics of the diet material [17] as the fermentation process works on the activity of anaerobic bacteria such as lactic acid bacteria (*Lactobacillus*). The activity of these bacteria causes a change in the qualitative characteristics of the diet material and increases its readiness. This is positively reflected in the performance of the birds as a result of the increased rate of digestion and absorption of nutrients by the birds.

The fermentation process with kiwi juice may have led to raising the level of active compounds in barley, especially phenolic and flavonoid compounds and vitamin C, as these substances support the intestinal flora of birds, which stimulates them to increase the effectiveness of digestive enzymes, thus increasing the process of benefiting from food [18].

Table 5. Effect of different levels of fermented barley with kiwi juice in broiler diets on body weight in different periods.

Treatments ¹	Body weight (g) at different age		
	10 days	24 days	35 days
G1	4.63±252.87	13,02±1082.37 ^{ab}	9.07±2115.15
G2	6.09±253.75	15.68±1050.71 ^b	17,06±2116.90
G3	3.42±255.20	7.64±1097.89 ^{ab}	9.39±2118.08
G4	8.86±253.62	37.14±1138.46 ^a	35,09±2126.44
Significant level	N. S	*	N. S

Means with different letters within the same column differ significantly at the ($P < 0.05$). ¹ treatment: G1 = control treatment (basal diet), G2 = basal diet + 10% fermented barley, G3 = basal diet + 20% fermented barley and G4 = basal diet + 30% fermented barley. NS, means there are no significant differences between the treatments.

Table 6. The effect of using different levels of fermented barley with kiwi juice in broiler diets on weight gain from the age of (0-35 days).

Treatments ¹	Weight gain (g) at different age			CWG
	10 days	24 days	35 days	
G1	4.63±213.37 A	9.66±829.50 AB	14.96±1032.78 AB	9.07±2075.65 A
G2	6.09±214,80 A	16,68±796.96 B	29,51±1066.20 A	17.05±2077.95 A
G3	3.42±215.35 A	4.80±842.68 AB	5.14±1020.19 AB	9.39±2078.23 A
G4	8.86±214.09 A	31,46±884.83 A	31,61±1020.19 A	35,09±2086.91 A
Significant level	N. S	*	*	N. S

Means with different letters within the same column differ significantly at the ($P < 0.05$). ¹ treatment: G1 = control treatment (basal diet), G2 = basal diet + 10% fermented barley, G3 = basal diet + 20% fermented barley and G4 = basal diet + 30% fermented barley. NS, means there are no significant differences between the treatments. CWG = Cumulative weight gain.

Table 7. The effect of using different levels of fermented barley with kiwi juice in broiler diets on feed consumption from the age of (0-35 days).

Treatments ¹	Feed intake (g) at different age			Cumulative feed consumption
	10 days	24 days	35 days	
G1	4.104±242.622 A	9.327±1300.62 A	31,238±1616.31 A	39.941±3159.56 A
G2	2.834±239,040 AB	21,352±1260.54 AB	24.602±1589.13 A	11,938±3088.70 A

Treatments ¹	Feed intake (g) at different age			Cumulative feed consumption
	10 days	24 days	35 days	
G3	2.996±238.412 AB	15.271±1225.00 B	14,601±1609.83 A	24.545±3073.24 A
G4	4.766±229.957 B	28,811±1262.20 AB	46.983±1625.92 A	73,549±3118.08 A
Significant level	*	*	N. S	N. S

Means with different letters within the same column differ significantly at the ($P < 0.05$). ¹ treatment: G1 = control treatment (basal diet), G2 = basal diet + 10% fermented barley, G3 = basal diet + 20% fermented barley and G4 = basal diet + 30% fermented barley. NS, means there are no significant differences between the treatments.

Table 8. The effect of using different levels of fermented barley with kiwi juice in broiler diets on feed conversion ratios from the age of (0-35 days).

Treatments ¹	Feed conversion ratios at different age			Cumulative feed conversion ratios
	10 days	24 days	35 days	
G1	0.034±1.1388 A	0.021±1.568 A	0.037±1.565 A	0.018±1.522 A
G2	0.018±1.114 A	0.016±1.582 A	0.025±1.492 A	0.007±1.486 A
G3	0.0248±1.108 A	0.0179±1.453 A	0.019±1.578 A	0.013±1.478 A
G4	0.026±1.077 A	0.044±1.430 A	0.087±1.652 A	0.030±1.494 A
Significant level	N. S	N. S	N. S	N. S

¹ treatment: G1 = control treatment (basal diet), G2 = basal diet + 10% fermented barley, G3 = basal diet + 20% fermented barley and G4 = basal diet + 30% fermented barley. NS, means there are no significant differences between the treatments.

It is noted from the data in Table (9) that there were no significant differences between all treatments in the numbers of harmful and beneficial bacteria, while there was a mathematical improvement in the numbers of beneficial bacteria for all barley replacement treatments when compared with the comparison treatment G1, The absence of significant differences between all treatments in the numbers of harmful and beneficial microorganisms is due to the fact that barley fermentation did not negatively affect the intestinal contents of intestinal flora, despite the presence of some inhibitors in raw barley seeds. However, the fermentation process improved the nutritional value of barley grains, which in turn improved and encouraged the growth of beneficial microorganisms, perhaps through the fact that the fermentation process makes the substance acidic, and when birds eat it, it makes it PH The intestine tends to be acidic, which encourages the growth of beneficial microorganisms.

Table 9. The effect of using different levels of fermented barley with kiwi juice in broiler diets in *E. coli* and *Lactobacilli* From the age of (0-35 days).

Treatments ¹	mean ± Standard error	
	<i>Lactobacilli</i> Log(cfu/g)	<i>E. Coli</i> Log(cfu/g)
G1	5.81 ±0.28	6.35 ±0.05
G2	6.39 ±0.33	6.32 ±0.03
G3	6.52 ±0.27	5.84 ±0.53
G4	6.29 ±0.08	5.61 ±0.37
Significant level	N. S	N. S

¹ treatment: G1 = control treatment (basal diet), G2 = basal diet + 10% fermented barley, G3 = basal diet + 20% fermented barley and G4 = basal diet + 30% fermented barley. NS, means there are no significant differences between the treatments.

Table 10. Effect of using different levels of fermented barley with kiwi juice in broiler diets on lipoproteins Lipid profile from the age of (0-35 days).

Treatments ¹	mean ± Standard error (mg/dl)				
	CHOLSTEROL (mg/dl)	TRIGLYCERIDE (mg/dl)	HDL (mg/dl)	VLDL (mg/dl)	LDL (mg/dl)
G1	127.65±3.34	46.62±3.77b	90.91±8.13	9.32±0.75b	27.42±9.66
G2	132.48±8.63	46.62±4.37b	95.75±7.48	9.32±0.87b	27.41±13.79
G3	132.73±9.31	71.06±9.10a	104.00±3.74	14.21±1.82a	14.52±8.69
G4	142.51±7.17	51.76±8.42ab	109.66±8.19	10.35±1.68ab	22.49±13.52
Significant level	NS	*	NS	*	NS

Means with different letters within the same column differ significantly at the ($P < 0.05$). 1 treatment: G1 = control treatment (basal diet), G2 = basal diet + 10% fermented barley, G3 = basal diet + 20% fermented barley and G4 = basal diet + 30% fermented barley. NS, means there are no significant differences between the treatments.

Table 11. Effect of using different levels of barley fermented with kiwi juice in broiler diets on glucose, total protein, albumin and globulin from the age of (0-35 days).

Treatments ¹	mean ± Standard error (mg/dl)			
	Glucose (mg/dl)	Total protein (g/dl)	The two albums (g/dl)	Globulin (g/dl)
G1	140.37±7.01	6.23±0.30	3.02±0.04	3.21±0.31
G2	144.14±6.91	5.92±0.12	3.07±0.04	2.85±0.13
G3	141.33±6.36	6.15±0.23	3.01±0.07	3.15±0.29
G4	135.53±4.78	5.97±0.05	3.06±0.05	2.91±0.06
Significant level	NS	NS	NS	NS

NS It means that there are no significant differences between the averages of the transactions.

Table 12. Effect of using different levels of barley fermented with kiwi juice in broiler diets on the concentration of liver enzymes ALT and AST From the age of (0-35 days).

Treatments ¹	mean ± Standard error	
	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)
G1	11.63±4.27b	21.96±4.71a
G2	20.79±8.19b	18.90±8.17ab
G3	18.32±5.36b	11.49±2.88ab
G4	37.66±7.22a	7.71±2.42b
Significant level	*	*

Averages with different letters within the same column are significantly different from each other. * ($P < 0.05$).

Regarding some physiological characteristics of the transactions, it is noted from Tables (10, 11, 12) that there are no significant differences in most blood characteristics, especially cholesterol, HDL, LDL also glucose, total protein, albumin, and globulin, while there were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) In the description of triglycerides and VLDL If the group's birds were recorded G3 Significant increase in the concentration of these two traits compared to the control group G1 and G2 While it did not differ with G4 as for liver enzymes, it is noted from the data in Table (12) that there was a significant increase in the concentration of ALT For treatment birds G4 Compared to all treatments while birds recorded the same treatment G4 morally lower ($P < 0.05$) Compared to control group G1 While it did not differ from what is found in the transactions G2 and G3.

The absence of negative effects of using fermented barley in broiler diet on some physiological blood characteristics is a good indicator and encourages the use of barley in higher proportions. This may be due to the use of kiwi juice in fermenting barley grains, as kiwi juice contains active compounds, especially phenols and flavonoids, in addition to the presence of vitamin C [11]. These compounds exhibit antioxidant activity that plays an important role in protecting biomolecules, nucleic acids, poly lipids, proteins and sugars from oxidative damage [20-21]. These compounds also protect the body's cells and muscle tissues from oxidation processes and the formation of free radicals, thus improving liver function. A significant decrease in the activity of AST Especially in the blood of birds and for the

fourth treatment G4 Compare with comparison birds' treatment G1 Note that the percentage of barley in the fourth treatment is 30%. there was a significant decrease with the increase in the percentage of use. Here, there was an increase in the percentage of active compounds due to fermentation, as the increase in these materials works to reduce the oxidation processes and thus reduces the activity of this enzyme.

Conclusion

Kiwi juice can be used to improve the nutritional value of low-nutritional-value feedstuffs, especially barley. Also, replacing yellow corn with fermented barley at the rate of 10, 20 and 30% did not negatively affect the performance of broiler chickens. Liver enzyme activity was positively affected in broilers fed on fermented barley.

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